

Rice grain yield was not affected by herbage removal. Panicles/m² increased significantly but spikelets/panicle, plant height, and biomass yield decreased significantly with increased cuttings. Fertility and 1,000-grain weight were not affected.

The ability to increase rice herbage yield by increasing cutting for herbage without detrimental effect on grain yield could benefit animal production, especially in rice cultivars with long growth duration. ■

Effect of cutting treatments on herbage yield, grain yield, and production components of PG56. Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Ayutthaya, Thailand, 1988 wet season.

Treatment ^b	Herbage yield (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Fertility (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Height at maturity (cm)	Biomass yield (t/ha)		
Control (no cut)	-	2.5	124	d 100	a	90	27.41	223 a	14.5 a	
One cutting, 40 DE	0.5	d 2.6	149	c	96	ab	85	27.14	214 ab	12.8 bc
One cutting, 70 DE	1.2	c 2.6	152	c	89	abc	87	28.01	202 bc	12.6 bc
One cutting, 100 DE	1.2	c 2.4	151	c	90	abc	88	28.83	201 bc	13.2 ab
One cutting, 130 DE	1.2	c 2.4	151	c	82	bcd	86	27.86	201 bc	13.0 bc
Two cuttings, 40+70 DE	1.4	bc 2.5	178	ab	75	cd	89	28.52	197 c	12.3 bc
Two cuttings, 40+100 DE	1.6	b 2.3	174	ab	72	cd	89	28.43	200 bc	12.3 bc
Two cuttings, 70+100 DE	1.9	a 2.3	162	bc	72	cd	85	28.11	194 c	11.5 c
Three cuttings, 40+70+100 DE	2.0	a 2.4	185	a	64	d	84	28.23	193 c	11.6 c

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bDE = days after emergence.

Fertilizer management

Effect on rice of placement depth of urea supergranules

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We evaluated the effects of placement of urea supergranules (USG) (5, 10, and 15 cm deep and broadcast prilled urea (PU) on rice yields of tall, long-duration Mahsuri and dwarf, short-duration Madhuri.

The trial was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications during 1987 rainy season.

Soil was an Entisol-Tropofluent, alluvial, deep and flat. It was clay loam with 52.50% sand, 24.75% silt, and 22.75% clay; moderately fertile with 324.80-26.34-174.24 kg available NPK; pH 7.0; and CEC 25 meq/100 g soil.

Plant spacing was 15 × 20 cm. N was applied at 38.32 kg/ha.

One 1-g granule of USG was deep-placed in the middle of each four hills in alternate rows; prilled urea was broadcast in three splits at sowing, maximum tillering, and panicle initiation in a 1:2:1 ratio.

N conversion efficiency (NCE) was computed as

$$\text{Nitrogen conversion efficiency} = \frac{\text{Yield for USG placement} - \text{yield for PU}}{\text{N applied (38.32 kg/ha)}} \times 100$$

Mahsuri had significantly higher yield than Madhuri, although some lodging occurred during late growth (Table 1). Mahsuri produced significantly higher panicles/m², panicle length and weight, filled spikelets/panicle, and 1,000-grain weight. The yield difference was probably due to Mahsuri's long duration, about 1 mo longer than Madhuri.

All depths of USG placement resulted in higher yield characters than broadcast PU; however, differences except for panicle length were not significant. The

cumulative effect resulted in significantly higher grain and straw yield with USG.

Placement depth did not affect yields. Probably the fine soil texture ensured uniform availability of N to roots at all depths, with higher cation exchange capacity and less leaching loss.

In N conversion efficiency, 10 cm placement of USG was most efficient in Mahsuri, and 15 cm placement in Madhuri (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Nitrogen conversion efficiency for USG.

Placement depth (cm)	N efficiency (%)	
	Mahsuri	Madhuri
5	7.0	18.1
10	18.4	8.7
15	2.6	19.1

Table 1. Effect of USG and prilled urea on characters and yield of rice.

Treatment	Panicle (no./m ²)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle weight (g)	Unfilled panicles (no.)	Filled spikelets (no./panicle)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Mahsuri	354	23	43	21	306	21	2.3	4.1
Madhuri	247	21	20	34	110	15	1.6	2.4
LSD ^a	64	1.4**	11**	ns	149**	3**	0.6*	1.8**
USG depth								
5 cm	319	23	32	24	218	10	2.1	3.4
10 cm	326	22	32	23	222	18	2.1	3.6
15 cm	290	23	31	29	206	18	2.0	3.3
PU broadcast	267	20	30	33	186	18	1.6	2.7
LSD ^a	ns	1	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.4**	0.7**

^aSignificant at 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels. NS = nonsignificant.

Fertilizer management – inorganic sources

Integrated phosphorus management in a rice-based cropping system

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We studied the effects of P management in a rice - rice - green gram cropping system. In first rice crop (variety IR50) Jun-Oct 1985, P at the recommended 22 kg P/ha was applied as superphosphate and rock phosphate, and no P alone and with 12 t/ha sunn hemp *Crotalaria*

juncea L., in a randomized block design with three replications.

The second rice crop (CO 43) Nov 1985-Feb 1986 was grown in a split-plot design, with no additional fertilizer and with the recommended 26 kg P/ha as

superphosphate and as rock phosphate in combination with incorporated stubble cut 10 cm and 25 cm high.

Green gram *Vigna radiata* L. Wilczek was grown Feb-May 1986 without fertilizer. A fourth crop rice Jun-Sep

1986 was grown with the treatments given the first crop rice, substituting green gram haulm for sunn hemp.

The Mussoorie rock phosphate used was analyzed as 1.48% citrate soluble P_2O_5 , and 20% total P_2O_5 . Soil was Typic Haplustalf with pH 8.1, 0.6% organic C, CEC 27 meq/100 g, and 16 kg available P/ha. Inorganic N and K fertilizers were applied at recommended levels.

In the first crop rice, green manure plus superphosphate gave higher yields (see table). In the second crop rice, yields were higher where the first crop had been given superphosphate with or without green manure and rock phosphate with green manure.

In the second crop rice, yield was higher with superphosphate and long stubble incorporation. Residual effects of treatments given the first rice crop on the green gram crop of treatments given the first rice crop were not significant.

Superphosphate with long or short stubble incorporation in the second crop improved green gram yield.

Yield of the fourth crop rice was significantly improved by green gram haulm incorporation; P application had no significant effect. ■

Yields of rice-based cropping system under integrated P management Coimbatore, India, 1985-86.

First crop rice Jun-Oct 1985		Second crop rice Nov 1985-Feb 1986		Third crop green gram Feb-May 1986		Fourth crop rice Jun-Sep 1986	
Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	Treatment ^a	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)
G ₀	4.4	G ₀ P ₀	4.4	G ₀ P ₀	393	G ₀	4.3
G ₁	5.2	G ₀ P _s	5.3	G ₀ P _s	400	G ₁	5.1
LSD (0.05)	0.4	G ₀ P _r	4.6	G ₀ P _r	456	LSD (0.05)	0.5
		G ₁ P ₀	4.9	G ₁ P ₀	443		
P ₀	4.4	G ₁ P _s	5.6	G ₁ P _s	499	P ₀	4.5
P ₅	5.3	G ₁ P _r	5.0	G ₁ P _r	451	P _s	4.9
P ₁	4.6	LSD (0.05)	0.6	LSD (0.05)	ns	P _r	4.6
LSD (0.05)	0.5					LSD (0.05)	ns
		S ₀ P ₀	4.7	S ₀ P ₀	390		
		S ₀ P _s	5.0	S ₀ P _s	500		
		S ₀ P _r	4.9	S ₀ P _r	412		
		S ₁ P ₀	4.7	S ₁ P ₀	405		
		S ₁ P _s	5.4	S ₁ P _s	515		
		S ₁ P _r	5.1	S ₁ P _r	421		
		LSD (0.05)	0.3	LSD (0.05)	70		

^aG₀ = no green manure, G₁ = green manure; P₀ = no phosphate, P_s = superphosphate, P_r = Rock phosphate; S₀ = 10-cm stubble incorporated, S₁ = 25-cm stubble incorporated.

Nitrogen loss by ammonia volatilization from urea and ammonium chloride in flooded soil

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Rapid hydrolysis of urea to ammonium carbonate can cause high concentrations of NH_4^+ -N and high floodwater pH, leading to high ammonia volatilization. In contrast, the low pH of ammonium chloride may help minimize ammonia volatilization from soils. We measured NH_3 volatilization from urea and ammonium chloride using the forced-draft chamber technique in the laboratory.

We used a set of 10-liter pots with 7 kg air-dried soil (pH 8.05, 0.32% organic C, 0.06% total N, CEC 9.5 meq/100 g). The soil was flooded, puddled, and allowed to preincubate with 1 cm

standing water for 1 wk. Pots were fertilized with 26 mg P and 50 mg K/kg applied as single superphosphate and muriate of potash.

Treatments were urea, urea + N-(n-butyl) thiophosphoric triamide (NBT) (2% wt/wt), ammonium chloride, and no N. N was applied at 200 kg/ha.

Soil was reflooded and evaporation losses replenished daily to maintain 5 cm standing water. Water temperatures ranged from 22.5 to 27.5°C.

Two pots/treatment were fitted with chambers continuously flushed with NH_3 -free compressed air. NH_3 was collected at intervals using a manifold and estimated by absorbing in 2% boric acid-mixed indicator solution. Floodwater was analyzed for ammoniacal N and pH.

N loss by ammonia volatilization was markedly affected by source of fertilizer (Fig. 1). In ammonium chloride-treated soil, ammonia volatilization was almost uniform up to 12 d after fertilizer applica-

1. Effect of urea, urea + NBT, and ammonium chloride on cumulative loss of ammonia from flooded sandy loam soil, Ludhiana, India.

tion. With urea alone, ammonia volatilization loss appeared within 5 d and rate increased up to 12 d, then decreased. With NBT-treated urea, ammonia volatilization was low up to 7 d, then increased consid-